

Soil and crop management

Deep placement of fertilizer phosphorus in rice

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Phosphate application significantly increased the rice yield of IR8, and 60 kg P₂O₅/ha (superphosphate) produced significantly more paddy than 30 kg P₂O₅/ha (see table 1) in a microplot field experiment in the Punjab Agricultural University rice research area. The soil of the experiment field was sandy loam with pH 8.4, E.C. 0.01 pmho/cm, organic carbon 0.384%, and Olsen's extractable P 10 kg/ha. Rice plants were spaced 20 x 15 cm. Superphosphate tagged with ³²P was applied in mudballs at transplanting, broadcast at transplanting, or topdressed 2 weeks after transplanting. The mudballs, (approx. 2.5 cm in diameter) were prepared by mixing superphosphate with soil and some water; they were pushed 7-9 cm deep into the soil at transplanting. A basal dose of 60 kg N/ha (as urea) and 60 kg K₂O/ha (as muriate of potash) was added at puddling, and an additional 60 kg N/ha was applied in equal parts 21 and 42 days after transplanting. The rice crop was raised under flooded conditions.

Fertilizer P uptake was also investigated at 6 weeks (maximum tillering), 8 weeks (between maximum tillering and panicle emergence), and 11 weeks (ear emergence) after transplanting.

The yield that was attributable to the P ranged from 360 to 720 kg/ha with 30 kg P₂O₅/ha, and from 550 to 1,470 kg/ha with 60 kg P₂O₅/ha.

Deep placement of 60 kg P₂O₅/ha at transplanting produced the highest yield; 30 kg P₂O₅/ha deep placed as mudballs yielded as well as 60 kg P₂O₅ broadcast at transplanting. The efficiency of fertilizer P was highest with deep placement as mudballs. At 60 kg P₂O₅/ha,

24.5 kg rice/kg P₂O₅ was produced with deep placement, 9.1 kg with broadcast at transplanting, and 9.6 kg with topdressing 2 weeks after transplanting.

P removal by grain was also highest with P buried in mudballs (table 2); it was significantly higher at the recommended dose of 60 kg P₂O₅/ha.

The relative efficiency of P application by different methods for yield and total P removal (table 2) was calculated using the relationship: $(Y_t = Y_o) / (Y_s - Y_o)$

Where

Y_t = yield or P removal in treatment under test

Y_o = yield or P removal in the control
 Y_s = yield or P removal in standard treatment.

For both grain yield and total P removal, deep placement at transplanting was the most efficient method of P application.

At 30 kg P₂O₅/ha, deep placement of P at transplanting resulted in the highest percentage of P in plant derived from the fertilizer in all three stages of plant growth (table 3).

The results indicate that IR8 taps applied P most efficiently when the P is placed in the immediate vicinity of the roots. IR8's shallow and compact rooting system makes that understandable. Deep placement may also result in minimum fixation of the applied P in the soil.

Table 1. Yield and total P removal by paddy grain as affected by different methods of P application. Punjab, India.

Treatment	Yield (kg/ha)			P removal by paddy grain (kg/ha)		
	30 kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha	60 kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha	Mean	30 kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha	60 kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha	Mean
Broadcast at transplanting	5187	5373	5280	12.75	14.47	13.61
Deep placement at transplanting	5326	6294	5810	12.69	16.75	14.72
Topdressing 2 weeks after transplanting	5542	5402	5472	13.20	14.63	13.91
Mean	5352	5689		12.88	15.28	
Control	4823			11.48		
C.D. (5%)						
for control vs. treatment	5.00			3.85		
for level	3.32			0.98		
for method	3.70			n.s.		

Table 2. Relative efficiency values of different methods of P application for paddy yield and total P removal by grain, Punjab, India.

Treatment	Relative efficiency value	
	Grain yield	P removal by grain
Broadcast at transplanting	100	100
Deep placement at transplanting	216	152
Topdressing 2 weeks after transplanting	142	114

Table 3. Phosphorus in plant derived from fertilizer. Punjab, India.

Treatment	P ₂ O ₅ (kg/ha)	Phosphorus (%) in plant		
		6WT ^a	8WT ^a	11WT ^a
Broadcast at transplanting	30	40	36	22
	60	40	35	35
Deep placement at transplanting	30	49	42	44
	60	27	20	19
Topdressing 2 weeks after transplanting	30	29	22	22
	60	38	24	25

^aWT = weeks after transplanting.